

Supplemental Materials

Supplemental Material A Social economy subsystem variable description and formula.

Variable	Unit	Formula	Description	Number
Population	Person	Min (INGET (Population increment, 20238000), 23000000)	-	Eq. (A.1)
Population increment	Person	Population * Growth rate of population	-	Eq. (A.2)
Growth rate of population	%	Initial growth rate of Population * Coefficient of population growth rate	-	Eq. (A.3)
Initial growth rate of Population	%	=2	-	Eq. (A.4)
Coefficient of population growth rate	-	IF THEN ELSE (Urban road traffic carbon emissions < 10000000, 1, 0.9)	-	Eq. (A.5)
GDP	yuan	INGET (GDP increment, 171888000000)	-	Eq. (A.6)
GDP increment	yuan	GDP * Growth rate of GDP	-	Eq. (A.7)
Growth rate of GDP	%	Initial of GDP growth rate * Coefficient of GDP growth rate	-	Eq. (A.8)
Initial of GDP growth rate	%	=8.10	-	Eq. (A.9)
Coefficient of GDP growth rate	-	IF THEN ELSE (Urban road traffic carbon emissions < 10000000, 1, 0.9)	-	Eq. (A.10)
Per capita GDP	Person/yuan	GDP/ Population	-	Eq. (A.11)

Supplemental Material B Urban form subsystem variable description and formula.

Variable	Unit	Formula	Description	Number
Number of buses	Car	$0.024 * TA - 71020.4 * COHESION + 780.93 * LSI + 2468.81 * POLYP + 0.05 * \text{Per capita GDP} + 6954672$		Eq. (B.1)
Number of private cars	Car	$\text{Min}(12.96 * TA - 7606375 * COHESION + 54975.55 * LSI - 254097.5 * POLYP + 15.82 * \text{Per capita GDP} + 7.48 * 100000000, 5800000)$	$R^2 = 0.996$	Eq. (B.2)
Number of taxis	Car	$-34374.88 * COHESION + 217.83 * LSI - 1775.13 * POLYP + 0.12 * \text{Per capita GDP} + 3449133$	$R^2 = 0.944$	Eq. (B.3)
Road length	km	$0.0326621 * TA - 98.5178 * LSI - 7831.87 * COHESION - 342.937 * POLYP + 0.003593 * \text{Per capita GDP} + 811479$	$R^2 = 0.941$	Eq. (B.4)
TA	-	$1.65 / 100000000 * \text{GDP} + 0.01 * \text{Population} + 85777.65$	$R^2 = 0.993$	Eq. (B.5)
COHESION	-	$2.12 / 10000000000000 * \text{GDP} + 4.97 / 1000000000 * \text{Population} + 99.74$	$R^2 = 0.879$	Eq. (B.6)
LSI	-	$-1.12 / 1000000000000 * \text{GDP} + 1.1 / 1000000 * \text{Population} + 168.4$	$R^2 = 0.700$	Eq. (B.7)
POLYP	-	$-1.93 / 100000000000000 * \text{GDP} + 1.1 / 10000000 * \text{Population} - 1.89$	$R^2 = 0.702$	Eq. (B.8)

Supplemental Material C Transportation development subsystem variable description and formula.

Variable	Unit	Formula	Description	Number
Urban road traffic intensity	-	Turnover of private cars + Turnover of taxi + Turnover of bus	-	Eq. (C.1)
Turnover of private cars	Car ·km	Private car trips * Average distance traveled by car	-	Eq. (C.2)
Private car trips	-	Number of private cars * Daily number of car trips	-	Eq. (C.3)
Turnover of bus	Car ·km	Number of buses * Average daily operating mileage of buses	-	Eq. (C.4)
Average daily operating mileage of buses	km	= 164.38	-	Eq. (C.5)
Turnover of taxi	Car ·km	Number of taxis * Daily operating mileage of taxis	-	Eq. (C.6)
Daily operating mileage of taxis	km	= 328.77	-	Eq. (C.7)
Urban road carrying capacity	Car ·km	Road length*1400*24	-	Eq. (C.8)
Network load	-	Urban road traffic intensity / Urban Road carrying capacity	-	Eq. (C.9)
Average vehicle speed	-	$125.19 * e^{(-0.7866 * \text{Network load})}$	-	Eq. (C.11)
Carbon emission factors of gasoline motor vehicles	-	$0.134 + 3.664 / \text{Average vehicle speed}$	-	Eq. (C.12)
Carbon emission factors of diesel buses	-	$0.575 + 16.207 / \text{Average vehicle speed}$	-	Eq. (C.13)
Carbon emission factors of new energy vehicles	-	Electric vehicle /100*Electric power emission factor I=16/100*0.884	-	Eq. (C.14)

Supplemental Material D Road traffic carbon emissions subsystem variable description and formula.

Variable	Unit	Formula	Description	Number
Urban road traffic carbon emissions	kg	Carbon emissions from private cars + Carbon emissions from buses + Carbon emissions from taxis	-	Eq. (D.1)
Carbon emissions from private cars	kg	(Carbon emissions of new energy vehicles + Carbon emissions from private gasoline cars) *365	-	Eq. (D.2)
Carbon emissions of new energy vehicles	kg	Number of new energy vehicles * Carbon emission factors of new energy vehicles * Daily number of car trips * Average distance traveled by car	-	Eq. (D.3)
Carbon emissions from private gasoline cars	kg	Number of private gasoline cars * Carbon emission factors of gasoline motor vehicles * Daily number of car trips * Average distance traveled by car	-	Eq. (D.4)
Number of private gasoline cars	Car	Number of private cars - Number of new energy vehicles	-	Eq. (D.5)
Carbon emissions from buses	kg	Number of buses * Average daily operating mileage of buses * Carbon emission factors of diesel buses *(1- Proportion of new energy buses) *365+ Number of buses * Average daily operating mileage of buses * Carbon emission factors of new energy vehicles * Proportion of new energy buses*365	-	Eq. (D.6)
Carbon emissions from taxis	kg	Number of taxis * Daily operating mileage of taxis * Carbon emission factors of gasoline motor vehicles*365	-	Eq. (D.7)

Supplemental Material E Scenario Setup.

Name	Description	Moderate Development Setting	Ideal Development Setting
BS	Base scenario	The number of various types of vehicles continued the historical trend (parameters extrapolated from 2011 to 2019), and there was no intervention from new emission reduction policies. The travel distance and emission level of all types of vehicles remain unchanged. The relationship between urban form and GDP and population remains unchanged.	
CT	Control TA	The annual urban land scale is 3% less than the original value. Other variables remain constant.	The annual urban land scale is 5% less than the original value. Other variables remain constant.
CC	Control COHESION	The annual compactness is 0.05% higher than the original value. Other variables remain constant.	The annual compactness is 0.12% higher than the original value. Other variables remain constant.
CL	Control LSI	The annual complexity is 0.5% lower than the original value. Other variables remain constant.	The annual complexity is 1.1% lower than the original value. Other variables remain constant.
CP	Control POLYP	The annual polycentricity is 12.3% higher than the original value. Other variables remain constant.	The annual polycentricity is 19.2% higher than the original value. Other variables remain constant.
CCL	Control COHESION and LSI	The annual compactness is 0.05% higher than the original value. The annual complexity is 0.5% lower than the original value. Other variables remain constant.	The annual compactness is 0.12% higher than the original value. The annual complexity is 1.1% lower than the original value. Other variables remain constant.
CCP	Control COHESION and POLYP	The annual compactness is 0.05% higher than the original value. The annual polycentricity is 12.3% higher than the original value. Other variables remain constant.	The annual compactness is 0.12% higher than the original value. The annual polycentricity is 19.2% higher than the original value. Other variables remain constant.
CCT	Control COHESION and TA	The annual compactness is 0.05% higher than the original value. The annual urban land scale is 3% less than the original value. Other variables remain constant.	The annual compactness is 0.12% higher than the original value. The annual urban land scale is 5% less than the original value. Other variables remain constant.
CLP	Control LSI and POLYP	The annual complexity is 0.5% lower than the original value. The annual polycentricity is 12.3% higher than the	The annual complexity is 1.1% lower than the original value. The annual polycentricity is 19.2% higher than the

		original value. Other variables remain constant.	original value. Other variables remain constant.
CTL	Control TA and LSI	The annual complexity is 0.5% lower than the original value. The annual urban land scale is 3% less than the original value. Other variables remain constant.	The annual complexity is 1.1% lower than the original value. The annual urban land scale is 5% less than the original value. Other variables remain constant.
CTP	Control TA and POLYP	The annual polycentricity is 12.3% higher than the original value. The annual urban land scale is 3% less than the original value. Other variables remain constant.	The annual polycentricity is 19.2% higher than the original value. The annual urban land scale is 5% less than the original value. Other variables remain constant.
CCLT	Control COHESION, LSI and TA	The annual compactness is 0.05% higher than the original value. The annual urban land scale is 3% less than the original value. The annual complexity is 0.05% lower than the original value. Other variables remain constant.	The annual compactness is 0.12% higher than the original value. The annual urban land scale is 5% less than the original value. The annual complexity is 1.1% lower than the original value. Other variables remain constant.
CCLP	Control COHESION, LSI and POLYP	The annual compactness is 1% higher than the original value. The annual complexity is 0.05% lower than the original value. The annual polycentricity is 12.3% higher than the original value. Other variables remain constant.	The annual compactness is 0.12% higher than the original value. The annual complexity is 1.1% lower than the original value. The annual polycentricity is 19.2 % higher than the original value. Other variables remain constant.
CTLP	Control TA, LSI and POLYP	The annual urban land scale is 3% less than the original value. The annual complexity is 0.5% lower than the original value. The annual polycentricity is 12.3% higher than the original value. Other variables remain constant.	The annual urban land scale is 5% less than the original value. The annual complexity is 1.1% lower than the original value. The annual polycentricity is 19.2% higher than the original value. Other variables remain constant.
CCTP	Control COHESION, TA and POLYP	The annual compactness is 0.05% higher than the original value. The annual urban land scale is 3% less than the original value. The annual polycentricity is 12.3% higher than the original value. Other variables remain constant.	The annual compactness is 0.12% higher than the original value. The annual urban land scale is 5% less than the original value. The annual polycentricity is 19.2% higher than the original value. Other variables remain constant.

CV Control all urban form Control scenarios were set for all urban form indicators. Other variables remain constant.
variables

Supplemental Material F Authenticity test result.

GDP (100 million yuan)				Population (10,000 person)				Number of buses (Car)			
Year	True value	Simulated value	Error rate (%)	Year	True value	Simulated value	Error rate (%)	Year	True value	Simulated value	Error rate (%)
2011	17188.8	17188.8	0	2011	2023.8	2023.8	0	2011	21628	21345	1.31
2012	18512.34	18302.6	1.13	2012	2077.5	2052.13	1.22	2012	22146	21620	2.38
2013	19937.79	19488.6	2.25	2013	2125.4	2080.86	2.09	2013	23592	21895	7.19
2014	21413.18	20751.7	3.08	2014	2171.1	2109.99	2.81	2014	23667	22170	6.33
2015	22890.69	22096.2	3.47	2015	2188.3	2139.54	2.23	2015	23287	22444	3.62
2016	24470.15	23528	3.85	2016	2195.4	2169.49	1.18	2016	22688	22716	0.12
2017	26134.12	25052.7	4.14	2017	2194.4	2199.86	0.25	2017	22688	22986	1.31
2018	27885.11	26676.1	4.34	2018	2191.7	2230.66	1.78	2018	24076	23256	3.41
2019	29586.10	28404.7	3.99	2019	2190.1	2258.16	3.11	2019	23685	23522	0.69
Number of private cars (Car)				Road length (km)				Number of taxis (Car)			
Year	True value	Simulated value	Error rate (%)	Year	True value	Simulated value	Error rate (%)	Year	True value	Simulated value	Error rate (%)
2011	3897000	4042050	3.72	2011	21347.1	21200.4	0.69	2011	66646	66635	0.01
2012	4075000	4144130	1.70	2012	21491.8	21310.4	0.84	2012	66646	67005	0.54
2013	4265000	4250050	0.35	2013	21673.3	21425.3	1.14	2013	67046	67393	0.52
2014	4372000	4360060	0.27	2014	21848.8	21545.3	1.39	2014	67546	67800	0.38
2015	4403000	4474110	1.62	2015	21885	21670.7	0.98	2015	68284	68229	0.08
2016	4528000	4592580	1.43	2016	22026	21801.8	1.02	2016	68484	68677	0.28
2017	4672000	4715710	0.94	2017	22226	21939	1.29	2017	68484	69148	0.97

2018	4790000	4843580	1.12	2018	22255.8	22082.6	0.78	2018	70035	69641	0.56
2019	4974000	4976510	0.05	2019	22365.9	22233.1	0.59	2019	71517	70158	1.90

Supplemental Material G Model validation statistics.

Variable	RMSE	RRMSE (%)	TIC
GDP (100 million yuan)	831.9361	3.5994	0.0180
Population (10,000 person)	41.6208	1.9351	0.0097
Number of buses (Car)	880.4537	3.8196	0.0193
Number of private cars (Car)	66832.6400	1.5046	0.0075
Road length (km)	219.6554	1.0029	0.0050
Number of taxis (Car)	557.4958	0.8163	0.0041